

Supplementary Fig. 1 Genus-level structures for NP and OP microbiota for healthy and diseased children. Hierarchical clustering for microbial samples were conducted based on euclidean distance. The sample name at the outermost is labeled according to site(NP/OP) and health status(HC/P).